

Table continued

Entry, culture	Whiteheads (%)
<i>Scented tall</i>	
HBC19	43.9
HBC143	42.9
Pak Basmati	41.9
HBC46	38.3
Basmati 370	35.1
HBC28	32.1
<i>New lines</i>	
IET12606	50.8
IET12604	37.3
Basmati No. 2	25.3
IET12602	22.7
IET12601	21.6
IET12607	19.3
IET12605	15.7
IET12608	12.0
IET12603	8.6
IET12609	6.7

table). None of the scented tall entries were promising.

New entries IET12609, IET12603, and IET12608 showed promise for resistance to the pest. □

Effects of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* on rice varieties in the greenhouse

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We screened 42 rice varieties and lines against WBPH using the seedling bulk test. Test lines were sown 20 seeds/row in 10-cm-long rows in 40- × 30- × 5-cm iron seedboxes filled with 3 cm of fine soil, in a randomized complete design with three replications.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after sowing with second- to third-instar WBPH nymphs at 5 nymphs/seedling. Plant damage was assessed when all plants of susceptible check TN1 had died.

Two lines showed moderate resistance to WBPH with damage score 3, and 21 lines were moderately susceptible with damage score 5 (see table). □

Reaction of rice varieties to WBPH under greenhouse conditions in 1991 wet season.

Variety	Damage score ^a
A21	3
IR50404-57-2-2-3	3
IR32843-92	5
IR49517-32	5
IR50404-47	5
OM746-13	5
IR44595-70	5
IR44592-62	5
OM44-5	5
OM201	5
OM723-11E	5
IR64	5
OM723-7	5
OM723-11M	5
IR70	5
OM742-15	5
IR52280-117-1-1-3	5
IR42W-211-1-2-2-3	5
IR53970-100-3-3-2	5
A20	5
A8	5
24A	5
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	9

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Pest resistance—other pests

Assessment of rice resistance and susceptibility to stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*

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We examined ways to assess rice resistance and susceptibility to stem nematode *D. angustus*, the cause of ufra. We screened selections, most of which were identified through the International Rice Ufra Screening Set (1985-89), in successive glasshouse trials against an isolate of *D. angustus* from Haugiang, Vietnam.

Inoculum consisting of 300 *D. angustus* nematodes and eggs was placed in water 10-12 d after sowing (10 cm deep) and confined close to each seedling, using a 6-mm-diam drinking straw. The straw was removed per 7 d. Symptom development was monitored daily and nematodes/plant

Diagrammatic representation of symptoms of *D. angustus*: A = susceptible, with severity rated 0-16, and B = resistant.

were counted 28 d after inoculation (DAI). This method was reliable, giving 100% infection of the susceptible check NC492 with 1,047 *D. angustus*/plant (mean of 68 plants, standard error of mean = 74).

Symptoms on the most recent leaf were classified every 7 d as resistant (incompatible) or susceptible (compatible). Severity of susceptible responses was scored on a scale of 0-16 (see fig., A). Some resistant seedlings exhibited

Proportion of plants of Rayada 16-06 showing resistant and susceptible symptoms, 28 d after inoculation with *D. angustus*.

Host response	Plants (%)	<i>D. angustus</i>	
		Mean no./plant	Range/plant
Resistant-immune	13	0	0
Resistant-hypersensitive	49	2	0-13
Susceptible	38	46	6-572